

Reduction of Ferric Ions by Charcoal

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Reduction of ferric chloride in presence of charcoal with acid, neutral, or alkaline surface has been studied in some details. The reaction obeys the bimolecular equation. It is sensitive to temperature, the temperature coefficient being close to 2. The capacity of the charcoal for the reaction initially decreases, but ultimately increases with increase in its *pH* value. A reasonable explanation has been suggested. The oxygen rendered available can be accounted for partly as gaseous carbon dioxide and partly as a surface complex that comes off as carbon dioxide on desorption at high temperatures. There is a limit beyond which charcoal cannot utilise the oxygen and this fixes the limit of its ultimate capacity for the reaction.

Vasntko¹ from his study of the reduction of ferric ions by charcoal concluded that the reducing ability of the charcoal varied inversely with its ability to catalyse the inversion of cane sugar. In other words, according to him, the activity of the charcoal for the reaction decreases with increase in its acidity. Heymann *et al.*² agreed with these findings. Garten and Weiss³, who hold similar views, to suggest that the reduction of ferric ions is the result of two reactions, one of which reaches completion rapidly whereas the other continues at a slow rate for a long time.

It appears that neither the mechanism of the reaction nor the exact role of the charcoal has been elucidated so far. The present communication describes a systematic study of the reduction of ferric chloride in presence of charcoal with acid, neutral, or alkaline surface and enables a proper understanding of the process.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of sugar charcoal, prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar by means of sulphuric acid, followed by exhaustive washings with hot distilled water, was used as such (referred to as 'original' in the text) as well as after degassing in vacuum at 750° and at 1200°. These samples, as has been shown⁴, differ appreciably in their surface acidity.

Procedure.—Charcoal (1 g.) was mixed with 100 ml of ferric chloride solution of a given concentration (varying from 0.1 to 1.0 *N* with *pH* values varying from 2.25 to 1.50) in a bottle of 600 ml capacity and the suspension allowed to stand in an incubator, maintained at a given temperature, with occasional shaking (for about 2 minutes after every one hour during the day time). After a specified period, the bottle was withdrawn and the gas con-

1. *Z. Zuckerind.*, 1928, 52, 221.
2. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1930, 187, 97.
3. *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1957, 7, 60.
4. Puri *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 67.

tained in it was sampled and analysed for its O_2 , CO , and CO_2 contents in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus in the usual way. Similar analyses in case of a blank experiment without the addition of charcoal showed that CO_2 and O_2 present in the bottle were almost the same as normally present in the same volume of air. These values were subtracted from the amounts of CO_2 and O_2 determined in the reaction bottle.

An aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was examined for its ferric and ferrous iron contents by the usual analytical methods. The sum of the ferric and ferrous iron always agreed, within experimental limits, with the amount added originally, showing that ferric ions as such were not taken up by the charcoal at all. Incidentally, the amount of ferric chloride reduced in the blank experiments in no case exceeded 0.3% of the amount originally added.

The residual charcoal was washed, dried at 120° , and evacuated at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace. The gases evolved were analysed for CO , CO_2 , and water⁵.

DISCUSSION

The amounts of ferric chloride reduced in presence of the 'original' sugar charcoal at 35° after different intervals of time are recorded in Table I. The reaction appears to be rather slow and tends to attain equilibrium after about 50 days. There appears to be no evidence for the view (Garten and Weiss) that the reduction of ferric ions by charcoal is the result of two distinct reactions, one fast and the other slow. On plotting graphically the amounts reduced against the corresponding time interval, it can be shown that all points fit on one smooth curve. Assuming the reaction to be bimolecular, the velocity coefficient is seen to remain fairly constant.

TABLE I

Reduction of ferric chloride in N/10 solution by 'original' sugar charcoal at 35° .

Time.	FeCl ₃ reduced (mg./g.).	$k = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$	Time.	FeCl ₃ reduced (mg./g.).	$k = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$
8 hours	16.20	1.858×10^{-8}	10 days	355.63	1.724
1 day	48.47	1.892	12	390.30	1.620
3 days	135.60	1.867	15	445.55	1.549
4	184.69	1.973	20	492.05	
5	208.98	1.812	30	550.10	
6	247.86	1.855	40	596.86	
8	283.70	1.704	50	607.84	

The reaction seems to have an appreciable energy of activation as it is fairly sensitive to temperature (Table II). It can be shown by simple calculations that the temperature coefficient of the reaction is about 2.

5. Puri et al., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 750.

TABLE II

Reduction of ferric chloride in N/10 solution by original charcoal at different temperatures after 12 hours.

Temp.	FeCl ₃ reduced (mg./g.)
0°	Nil
25°	13.2
35°	25.9
50°	74.8
70°	239.14

The effect of concentration is shown in Table III. The reaction in each case was allowed to proceed for 31 days at 25°. The magnitude of the reaction, in case of each charcoal, increases with increase in concentration of the solution, but ultimately tends to approach a certain limiting value. It appears therefore that charcoal does not act as a catalyst in the ordinary sense of the term. It is more likely that it takes part in the reaction as a result of which it is changed into a form in which it is incapable of 'reacting' further.

TABLE III

Reduction of ferric chloride in solution of diff. conc. at 25° by the various samples of charcoal.

Conc. of the soln.	Amount of ferric chloride reduced after 31 days (mg./g.)		
	Original charcoal. (pH 2.85).	750°-evacuated charcoal. (pH 6.95).	1200°-evacuated charcoal. (pH 8.80).
0.10 N	356.3	340.2	210.6
0.30	542.6	429.3	226.8
0.50	656.1	469.8	259.2
0.75	737.0	499.1	299.7
1.00	748.1	510.3	299.7
	Amount of ferric chloride reduced after 48 hours.		
0.10	48.6	65.3	77.7

The activity to reduce ferric ions appears to decrease in the order: original charcoal > 750°-evacuated charcoal > 1200°-evacuated charcoal. Now, since the original charcoal has acid reaction in aqueous suspension (pH 2.85) whereas 750°- and 1200°-evacuated charcoals have neutral and alkaline reactions (pH 6.95 and 8.80) respectively, it is evident that contrary to the observations of previous workers, the ability of the charcoal for the reaction *decreases* with decrease in its acidity (or increase in alkalinity).

In order to examine the comparative efficiencies during the initial stages of the reaction, another run with a solution of one of the concentrations (0.1 N) was made for 48 hours only. The results are included in Table III at the bottom. It is seen that now the order of comparative efficiencies is just the opposite of that stated above. The ability of the charcoal for the reaction increases with decrease in acidity (or increase in alkalinity) as reported by Vasatko¹ and Heymann *et al.*² These workers, it will be seen, had based their conclusions on observations extended only to 3 hours and 18 hours respectively.

The reason for these anomalies may readily be understood from the following. The reduction of ferric chloride proceeds according to the equation:

Now charcoal can adsorb small amounts of hydrochloric acid from aqueous solution and its capacity to do so increases with decrease in the acidity of its surface⁶. Thus the 1200°- and 750°-evacuated charcoals will be in better position than the original charcoal to shift the equilibrium to the right in the initial stages. The ultimate capacity of the charcoal for the reaction will, however, depend on its capacity to utilise the oxygen and in this respect the original charcoal has been shown to be more reactive than the degassed materials⁷. Hence the order of efficiency ultimately is just the reverse of that initially.

TABLE IV

Account of oxygen rendered available from the reduction of FeCl₃ in diff. cases.

Conc. of the soln.	FeCl ₃ reduced (mg./g.)	O ₂ rendered available (mg./g.)	O ₂ evolved as gaseous CO ₂ (mg./g.)	O ₂ chemisorbed by charcoal and evolved as CO ₂ on evacuation (mg./g.)	Total O ₂ accounted for (mg./g.)
1	2	3	4	5	4+5
Original charcoal.					
0.10 N	358.3	17.54	12.57	4.74	17.31
0.30	542.6	26.71	16.07	10.40	26.47
0.50	658.1	32.30	16.22	16.11	32.33
0.75	737.0	36.28	16.28	20.20	36.48
750°-evacuated charcoal.					
0.10	340.2	16.75	6.07	10.45	16.52
0.30	429.3	21.14	8.57	12.60	21.17
0.50	469.8	23.13	8.78	14.30	23.08
1200°-evacuated charcoal.					
0.10	210.6	10.37	5.28	4.82	10.10
0.30	226.8	11.16	5.85	5.04	10.99
0.50	259.2	12.76	6.43	5.92	12.35

The examination of the gas in the reaction bottle did not reveal the presence of any free oxygen in excess of that obtained in the blank. There was also no evidence for the formation of carbon monoxide. Appreciable amounts of carbon dioxide were, however, observed in every case. The residual charcoal on evacuation at 1200° was found to evolve more carbon dioxide than before although there was no change in the amounts of carbon monoxide or water. This shows that a certain amount of oxygen is chemisorbed by the charcoal during the reaction and that this oxygen comes off as carbon dioxide on high-temperature evacuation. It will be seen on reference to Table IV that the oxygen

6. Steenberg, Ph.D. thesis, 1944, Stockholm University; Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.

7. Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 181.

rendered available from the reduction of ferric chloride at each concentration can be accounted for partly as gaseous carbon dioxide and partly as chemisorbed oxygen that comes off as carbon dioxide on desorption. The oxygen used up in the oxidation of charcoal to form gaseous carbon dioxide assumes a constant value much sooner than that chemisorbed by the charcoal. This shows that combustion of the surface proceeds sooner than its oxidation. But, evidently, there is a limit beyond which neither of the two reactions can proceed further. And this fixes the limit of the capacity of the charcoal to reduce ferric ions.

The original charcoal appears to have more 'active sites' than the 750°- and 1200°-evacuated charcoals along the surface, for these reactions.

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